

Impact of Quality Assurance On Teachers' Productivity in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools Education District V, Nigeria

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Abstract

The work examined the impact of quality assurance on teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Lagos State Education District V. The purpose was to find out the relationship between quality assurance and teachers' productivity. Correlational survey design was adopted to guide the study. Three research null hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. The population of the study comprised all secondary school teachers in Lagos State Education District V. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test all the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance). Findings showed that there is no significant relationship between quality assurance and attendance of teachers in school to a great extent influences the academic performance of students. Also, the activities of quality assurance team help teachers in the delivery of school curriculum which invariably improve students' academic performance. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made: the quality assurers must work together with the teachers almost on a regular basis to impinge on school effectiveness. Government should organize workshops and seminars for teachers to enable them developed professionally, more funds should be allocated to schools to enable them provide the needed facilities to enable the students perform better and teachers should be encouraged through incentives and frequent workshops and seminars to increase their output.

Keywords: Quality Assurance, Productivity, Curriculum Delivery, Classroom Management,

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Accepted 15 May 2020
Published 30 May 2020
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3877524

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1. Introduction

Education is a process of human understanding and accreditation, for the accomplishment of better, lofty and quality life of a state and her citizens. It is important therefore to say that education is shaped and moulded by the teacher, who plays a pivotal role in any educational system. This is in consonance with Adu, Oshati and Eze (2012) who submitted that there is no nation greater than the quality of her teachers. For a nation to rise to a barometer that is adequate enough for her to compete favourably in the comity of nations, such a state must ensure that there is high quality of teachers in her education industry. However, quality of teachers in the education sector brings quality education which will be instrumental to the indispensable transformation of individual worth, beliefs and attitudes; it is also used to maintain societal cultural settings and acquisition of skills that make members of the society useful to themselves and their society.

According to Ehusani (2002), the process of educating is to develop the cognitive, affective and psychomotor facilities of individuals and groups in order to equip them with knowledge and skills necessary to survive and make society progress. Aghenta, as cited by Ijaiya (2009), agrees that trained or educated human resources constitute man power and personnel that bring about national development. This is simply saying that the amount of educated citizen is equal to the amount of available quality work force that will contribute to a nation's development. Meanwhile, the quality of the workforce in the school system presupposes the quality of the school output, that is, the human resources that will be available for the nation. In the school system, some determinants of high quality education include goals of education, quality of the input as well as a well-organized school system that ensures the articulation and effective co-ordination of all aspects of school life (Ochuba 2009).

In Nigeria, the belief that teachers play a very central part in producing quality education has been adopted not only by educationists, but also by governments as well as community members (Abdul, 2011). The preparation of such important function of teachers ought to get the highest priority, which is training of the trainees. Unfortunately, the professional education of teachers has been completely neglected in the post-independence period. Educationists, policymakers, and parents in Nigeria also hold the view that good teachers produce good students. Dozier (2000), believed that the victory is in the classroom. He understood that the highest standards, the strongest accountability measures, the latest technology, and the most beautiful facilities will do little good without talented, dedicated, and well-prepared and educated teachers.

The quest for quality improvement in education service delivery necessitated the application of quality system management standards in the education sector. The adoption of quality assurance in education as an emerging policy perspective in the contemporary world emanated at the World Conference on Education for All led by United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in Jomtien, Thailand, in 1990. Representatives of the international community agreed that all countries should pay greater attention towards improving all aspects of the quality of education and ensuring excellence of all. This is to ensure substantial achievement of recognized and measurable learning outcomes in schools, especially in literacy, numeracy and essential life skills (UNESCO, 2002). Quality assurance, therefore, is one of the most critical tasks facing every nation's educational institutions, so that the societal demands for improved education service delivery would achieve the best learning outcomes that enhance the quality of life of the citizenry (Ayeni, 2010).

According to Merriam-Webster's Online Dictionary, quality assurance is "A programme for the systematic monitoring and evaluation of the various aspects of a project, service, or facility to ensure that standards of quality are being met". (Merriam-Webster, as cited by Ameen, 2007). Oakland (1993) defines quality assurance as the preventing of quality problems through planned and systematic activities. This will include the establishment of a good quality management system and the assessment of its adequacy, the audit of the operation of the system, and the review of the system itself.

Quality assurance practice therefore, involves setting attainable standards for instructional delivery process, organizing teaching and learning activities so that education objectives are achieved.

When the teachers' productivity declines, it has a correlation to the standard of education in schools both in the short and the long term. Teachers exert a great influence on the students, and the children look up to them for guidance, support and protection. Children are supposed to learn from them informally by observing their attitude, mannerism, conduct and general behaviours and formally through their teaching in the classrooms (Adu, 2015).

Teachers play a pivotal role in the education sector. It is widely believed that there is no nation greater than the quality of her teachers. For an education system to achieve the desired goals and objectives, the teachers' efficiency must be taken into consideration. The future of any educational level depends not only on the psychological factors but also the emotional factors of the teachers (Adu, Oshati & Eze, 2012).

It is against this background that this research work is embarked upon to examine the impact of quality assurance on teachers' productivity in senior secondary schools in education district V, Lagos State.

There is a growing concern of the society about the realization of secondary education objectives due to doubt that there have been steady decline in teachers' instructional task performance and students' academic performance which depicts non-realization of quality assurance in secondary schools (Adeniji, 2002). This has been attributed to gaps in teachers' competence, curriculum instruction, learning facilities and resources, funding and institutional management. Findings from literature (Ayeni & Akinola, 2008; Ipaye, 2002; Ogunu, 2001; Okebukola, 1996 and Zobaida, 2008) revealed that quality assurance in education is being affected by many problems. The effectiveness of a school system is measured from the output of the school, that is, the level of students' performance in both internal and external examinations, which is hinged among other things on the quality of teachers' input. Managing teachers for higher quality input, therefore, requires a strategy that will ensure that all aspects of school life are properly dove-tailed and effectively coordinated.

2. Purpose of the Study

This study seeks to find out the existing relationship between quality assurance and teachers' productivity in senior secondary schools in Education District V, Lagos State. In specific and explicit terms, this study sets out to:

- i. investigate the impact of Quality Assurance on teachers' attendance in school in public senior secondary schools in Education District V of Lagos State.
- ii. find out how Quality Assurance impact positively on teachers' delivery of school curriculum in public senior secondary schools in Education District V of Lagos State.
- iii. examine the impact of Quality Assurance on teachers' classroom management in public senior secondary schools in Education District V of Lagos State.

3. Research Questions

The following questions are raised to guide this study

1. Is it true that Quality Assurance has positive effect on teachers' attendance in school in public senior secondary schools in Education District V of Lagos state?
2. How does Quality Assurance affect teachers' delivery of school curriculum in public senior secondary schools in Education District V of Lagos state?
3. How does Quality Assurance has positive impact on teachers' classroom management in public senior secondary schools in Education District V of Lagos state?

4. Research Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between Quality Assurance and teachers' attendance in school in public senior secondary schools in Education District V, Lagos State.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between Quality Assurance and teachers' delivery of school curriculum in public senior secondary schools in Education District V, Lagos State.

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between Quality Assurance and teachers' classroom management in public senior secondary schools in Education District V, Lagos State.

5.1 Review of Literature

5.1.1 Quality Assurance in Education

Quality assurance in education is the efficient management, monitoring, evaluation and reviews of the resource inputs and transformation process (teaching and learning) to produce a quality output (students) that meets set standards and expectations of the society (Ayeni,2012). Quality assurance in other words is seen as the process of ensuring effective resource input, control, refining the process and raising the standard of output in order to meet the set goals and satisfy public accountability. Furthermore, quality assurance in education aims at preventing quality problems and ensures that the products of the system conform to the expected standards. Thus, the quality of teacher education is the degree of excellence of the input by teachers which is basically achieved through effective funding and provision of in-service training of teachers for quality assurance to be ascertained in teacher education.

Quality assurance agents are groups of individuals assigned with the responsibility of positive execution of government educational policies and programmes, implementation and evaluation for the purpose of continuous quality assurance and maintenance for the production of relevant and employable graduates for the society. These agents for quality assurance are concerned with, teaching and learning, students' assessment, staff development, curriculum/courses and physical resources. Quality assurance is not only concerned with the existence of these resources but should ensure that they are coherent and interrelated (Birzea, Cecclini, Krek, & Vrkas, 2005). They stated that a good quality assurance system in educational institutions should carry out the following functions:

1. Define specifically the purpose and nature of education provision, by identifying the gap between quality and how it may be measured.
2. Give responsibility and authority to ensure quality to school heads and teachers.
3. Create and control a good accountability system for daily work in school administration for the attainment of high standard (Birzea et al, 2005).

The framework for quality assurance according to them is in three states as follows:

- i. **Institutional Level:** This level should develop a conducive school climate for quality education.
- ii. **External Quality Assurance:** Is made up of school inspection; accreditation and evaluation.

iii. **Internal Quality Assurance:** Is concerned with the academic programme and development which depends on a continuous daily activity with designed guidance.

In education, quality emphasizes teachers' competence, creativity and commitment, and how educational administrators organize school activities in order to realize the full potentials of all personnels in educational institutions. It is the appropriateness and relevance of resources available for the achievement of educational goals and priorities, hence quality in education whether primary school, secondary school, or tertiary institutions require adequate inputs and output (Onyednachi, 2011). To ensure standards in these areas, academic institutions require qualified teachers who are well motivated. They also require quality students, conducive physical environment, well-equipped laboratories, workshops, libraries, instructional materials in the ideal quality and quality as well as funds for research and community service (Wokocho, 2009).

5.1.2 Techniques of Quality Assurance in Education

The techniques used for quality assurance in education include: monitoring, evaluation, supervision, inspection, quality control, access and equality.

Monitoring: Is referred to "an ongoing process by which stakeholders obtain regular feedback on the progress being made towards goals and objectives" (United National Development Programme, 2009). Monitoring is an essential source of information for programme evaluation.

Evaluation: Is the assessment of collected information in order to determine the value of judgments and/or generate knowledge to inform decisions about future programmes. Evaluation may be formative, providing feedback for improvement, or summative, assessing merit or worth. It may be internal conducted by programme staff such as monitoring and evaluation officers in development programmes, or external, conducted by outside evaluators who provide third party validation of special interest. Monitoring and evaluation are used by governments worldwide to improve school systems as they play integral role in the holistic transformation of education. Monitoring and evaluation can help transform educational programmes and measure quality indicators toward educational outcomes, increase stakeholders' participation, and empower school leaders and teachers to build and sustain transformation in schools. As each educational system is unique, evaluators should be prepared to vary their evaluation approach based on the purpose and context (Ijaiya, 2001).

Supervision: Supervision is a way of stimulating, guiding, improving, refreshing, encouraging and overseeing certain groups with the hope of seeking their cooperation in order for the supervisors to be successful in their task of supervision. Supervision is essentially the practice of monitoring the performance of school staff, observing the advantages and disadvantages with the aim of using befitting and good techniques to ameliorate the deficiencies while still improving on the advantages thereby increasing the school standards and achieve educational goals (Onocha, 2002).

Inspection: Inspection could be described as the critical examination and evaluation of a school (Ojelabi, 2011). Through inspection, necessary and relevant advice may be given for the improvement of the school. Usually, inspection involves an assessment of available human and material resources in an institution in order to establish how far the institution has met prescribed standards, it is more of an assessment rather than an improvement induced exercise (West-Burham, 2004).

Quality Control: The issue of quality control cannot be over-emphasized. It is one of the techniques for establishing quality assurance in the educational system at all levels. Ojedele

(2007) stated; that quality control should be the concern of the country in its drive towards technological and scientific development.

Access and Equity: Ojedele (2007) asserts that the trend of students transiting from the junior secondary school to other levels of education has not been encouraging as it has been falling short of the expectation. He further said that, the issue at the tertiary level presents a situation that calls for concerns in terms of variation in access at the Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Education and in terms of gender disparity. Implementing quality assurance techniques in education engenders a successful administration in the school.

Several empirical studies revealed that application of quality assurance to educational system in both developing and developed countries has resulted in quality improvement in the school system (Thakkar, Deshmukh & Shastree, 2006); Ojedele, 2007; Temponi 2005). Training of staff has been proved by various studies as motivator of performance, as innovatively prepared principals rated their learning significantly higher in all areas (Orr, 2006). The classroom becomes the clinic through which the expected societal values are remedy. Okorie and Agabi (2002) emphasized that the classroom instructional activities remain the core of the entire school system and its management no doubt form the nucleus of the entire school system managerial process. The performance of good classroom operations determines the administrative measure of the school administration. A quality school administration is ascertained from the good organizational classroom network. As Agabi (2002) noted the quality of a school's product is determined first by the quality of students admitted into the school, calibre of teachers, quality of instructional material, resource maintenance and teaching – learning environment, therefore the quality of any school administration is first determined by the quality of staff, students, resource availability, classroom management and instructional processes in the school.

6. Methodology

In designing the method for this study, correlational and descriptive research designs are considered suitable. This is because the study makes an attempt to describe quality assurance and teachers' productivity in Senior Secondary schools in Education District V, Lagos State. The study also describes the interplay between the variables.

The study population comprises all Senior Secondary Schools in Education District V in Lagos state. There are 66 Senior Secondary Schools in Education District V of Lagos State. The study population therefore consists of all teachers of these Schools. There are 1,821 teachers in Education District V.

The stratified random sampling technique was used to select thirty percent (30%) of total number of Senior Secondary Schools in Education District V, Lagos State. That is, for the teachers, 30 percent of them, after stratifying into zones. Therefore, ten (10) teachers were randomly selected as participants in the twenty schools that were selected for this study. Therefore, a total of 200 teachers were used for the study.

The instrument for data collection was teachers' questionnaire on quality assurance and teachers' productivity. The questionnaire was titled, Quality Assurance and Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire (QAATPQ). It was divided into two parts; the first part was on bio-data while the second part contain structured-item, statements that was used to elicit information from respondents regarding quality assurance and teachers' productivity in the schools that were sampled and it was patterned in Likert-type four points – scale, Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strong Disagree (SD).

All data to be collected from the respondents was analyzed by using descriptive (simple percentage will be used for demographic data) and inferential Statistics (Pearsons Product-Moment Correlation was used to test all the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance). Above all, the computerized Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used in the data analysis.

7. Results

Hypothesis I

There is no significant relationship between Quality Assurance and teachers' attendance in school in public senior secondary schools in Education District V, Lagos State.

Table 4.1 Correlation test between Quality Assurance and Teachers' attendance in school.

		Quality Assurance	Teachers' Attendance in School
Quality Assurance	Pearson Correlation	1	.089
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.322
	N	290	290
Teachers' Attendance in School	Pearson Correlation	.089	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	290	290

Source: Field Work (2020)

Table 4.1 presents the correlation test between Quality Assurance (*QA*) and teachers' attendance in school. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (0.089) indicates that there is a positive correlation between Quality Assurance (*QA*) and Teachers' Attendance in school. This test of correlation is significant since the p-value (0.322) is more than 5% (0.05). Therefore, there is significant relationship between Quality Assurance (*QA*) and Teachers' Attendance in school. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis II

There is no significant relationship between Quality Assurance and teachers' delivery of school curriculum in public senior secondary schools in Education District V, Lagos State.

Table 4.2 Correlation test between Quality Assurance and Teachers' delivery of school curriculum

		Quality Assurance	Teachers' Delivery of School curriculum
Quality Assurance	Pearson Correlation	1	.718
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.322
	N	290	290

Teachers' Attendance in School	Pearson	.718	1
	Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	290	290

Source: Field Work (2020)

Table 4.2 presents the correlation test between Quality Assurance (QA) and teachers' delivery of school curriculum. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (.718) indicates that there is a very positive correlation between Quality Assurance (QA) and Teachers' delivery of school curriculum. This test of correlation is significant since the p-value (.718) is more than 5% (0.05). Therefore, there is insignificant relationship between Quality Assurance (QA) and Teachers' delivery of school curriculum. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis III

HO₄: There is no significant relationship between Quality Assurance and teachers' classroom management in public senior secondary schools in Education District V, Lagos State.

Table 4.3 Correlation test between Quality Assurance and Teachers' classroom management

Correlations

		Quality Assurance	Teachers' Classroom Management
Quality Assurance	Pearson	1	.608
	Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.322
	N	290	290
Teachers' Attendance in School	Pearson	.608	1
	Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	290	290

Source: Field Work (2020)

Table 4.3 presents the correlation test between Quality Assurance (QA) and teachers' classroom management. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient indicates that there is a positive correlation between Quality Assurance (QA) and Teachers' classroom management. This test of correlation is significant since the p-value (.608) is more than 5% (0.05). Therefore, there is significant relationship between Quality Assurance (QA) and Teachers' classroom management. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

8. Discussion

In hypothesis one, the consistent presence of the teacher in the classroom is of supreme importance to provide effective instruction to students. Some research has suggested that high employee absenteeism indicates poor worker morale (Lippman *et al*, 1996). In addition, some research looks specifically at absenteeism in relation to how teachers report their absences. This research established that teachers are most likely to be absent less often if they are required to notify their principal by telephone about impending absences. (Miller, 2012). Research also shows that when a teacher is absent from the classroom, student learning is disrupted. Finlayson (2009) finds that when a teacher is repeatedly absent,

student performance can be significantly impacted negatively. Her study shows that the more days a teacher is out of the classroom, the lower their students score on every test. She measured the relationship between third grade teacher absenteeism and third-grade student scores on the math and reading sections on the Criterion Reference Competency Test (CRCT). She also reports that, nationally, teachers are absent from the classroom on average ten days per year.

The result on obtained on hypothesis two in showed that there is a significant relationship between teachers' classroom instructional tasks in terms of teachers' delivery of school curriculum and students' academic performance. It could be inferred from this finding that teachers' classroom instructional tasks have positive influence on students' academic performance. It is evident that the scheduled visits of quality assurance to various schools engender the delivery of school curriculum. This finding is supported by Hughes (2003) and Wenglinsky (2004) who found that students who have access to adequate material resources and taught by highly qualified teachers with instructional quality have stronger achievement in mathematics than their peers. This means that the more effective teachers are in the delivery of instructional activities, the better the students' academic achievement. The effect of these inadequacies on the curriculum coverage and students' academic performance is outrageous. Little can be expected of students who are not comprehensively groomed on the curriculum contents before sitting for examinations, with teachers who are over laboured with excess workload due to shortage of teachers.

The findings of hypothesis three showed that there is a significant relationship between quality assurance and teachers' classroom management. This implied that teachers made good use of classroom management strategies. This is supported by Brannon (2010) who found that there is a significant relationship between quality assurance and teachers' classroom management which in turn positively affect students' success in secondary schools. The activities of quality assurance team with the teacher in a given class help the teacher to control and manage the class effectively.

9. Conclusion

The study concludes that the consistent downward slide in the academic performance of students is largely attributed to the poor state of school variables. Quality Education Assurance Agency, although basically charged with monitoring and supervision of these school variables and reporting same to the government, who has the prerogative to decide what to do with the reports. The Agency can perform its statutory duties better, if the school variables are adequate and in good condition. Adequate teachers, standard and well equipped libraries and laboratories, adequate and conducive classrooms and relevant instructional materials are actually the responsibility of the Government in conjunction with parents, philanthropists and education stakeholders within the school environment. Therefore, Government and other relevant education stakeholders should be proactive in ensuring adequacy of all school variables, as this will ensure that the transformational process improves logically and the overall students' academic performance since concentration on quality assurance or supervision alone cannot guarantee the educational goals the state needs.

10. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are therefore recommended.

1. The quality assurers must work together with the teachers almost on a regular basis to impinge on school effectiveness.

2. The school head as the accounting officer of the school must ensure teachers' promotion as and at when due, and provide other incentives relevant to the effectiveness of his school in terms of students' achievement.
3. Provision of classrooms, furniture, equipped libraries and laboratories and teaching materials should be adequately made to promote a conducive learning environment.
4. Government should organize workshops and seminars for school administrators to upgrade their administrative capacity.
5. More funds should be allocated to schools to enable them provide the needed facilities to enable the students perform better.
6. Teachers should be encouraged through incentives and frequent workshops and seminars to increase their output.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), ORUNBON, NURUDEEN OLALEKAN, & ISAAC-PHILIPS MARGARET MODUPE, (2020). "Impact of Quality Assurance On Teachers' Productivity in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools Education District V, Nigeria." **Name of the Journal:** Commonwealth Journal of Academic Research, (CJAR.EU), P, 43- 55. **DOI:**

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3877524> , Issue: 2, Vol.: 1, Article: 4, Month: May, Year: 2020.

Retrieved from <https://www.cjar.eu/all-issues/>

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